

MEDICAL SCIENCES

ПАТОМОРФОЛОГІЧНІ ОСОБЛИВОСТІ ЗМІН СЛИЗОВОЇ ОБОЛОНКИ ШЛУНКОВО-КИШКОВОГО ТРАКТУ ПРИ COVID-19 ЗА ДАНИМИ ВЛАСНИХ ГІСТОЛОГІЧНИХ ТА ЛІТЕРАТУРНИХ ДОСЛІДЖЕНЬ

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PATHOMORPHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF CHANGES IN THE MUCOUS MEMBRANE OF THE GASTROINTESTINAL TRACT IN COVID-19 ACCORDING TO THE DATA OF OWN HISTOLOGICAL AND LITERARY STUDIES

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АННОТАЦІЯ

З початком пандемії Covid-19 основними симптомами захворювання були постійний кашель та лихоманка, проте зі збільшення кількості хворих і появою нових штамів вірусу, з'явилися нові симптоми. Понад 50% пацієнтів відчували на собі принаймі один симптом з боку ШКТ. Вплив вірусу на кишківник стає дедалі очевиднішим і потребує детального вивчення, оскільки були виявлені закономірності між наявністю симптоматики та преморбідного анамнезу з боку шлунково-кишкового тракту і важкістю перебігу ковіду.

Мета дослідження – дослідити патоморфологічні особливості ураження слизової оболонки шлунково-кишкового тракту при COVID-19 та їх вплив на розвиток ускладнень, зокрема токсико-інфекційного шоку.

Матеріали і методи. Проведено аналіз наукової літератури та гістологічні дослідження тканин слизової оболонки ШКТ 8-х пацієнтів, померлих від ускладнень інфекції SARS-CoV-2 в лікарнях Тернопільської області.

Результати дослідження. При морфологічному аналізі змін слизової оболонки ШКТ спостерігалися різні, за часом, ураження — від ознак гострого катарального запалення з початком зниження слизоутво-

рення, десквамацією епітелію, формуванням поверхневих ерозій до наявності ділянок із глибоким ерозивним слизовою оболонкою. У порожній кишці було виявлено ділянки епіталізації з тенденцією до атрофії. А також, потовщені оголені ворсини зі стромальною фібропластичною реакцією, деякі з них утворювали поліпоподібні вирости з епітелізованою поверхнею. Досліджуючи інтрамуральні нервові ганглії, знайдено признаки нейродегенеративних процесів.

Висновок. Описана морфологічна картина порожньої кишки характерна для підгострого запального процесу з фібропластичною реакцією, що є свідченням виникнення змін у ШКТ раніше, ніж у легенях. Щодо нейродегенеративних процесів у стінці кишківника, то вони характерні для хвилеподібного перебігу захворювання з бідною клінічною симптоматикою. Проаналізувавши наведені результати, можна зробити висновок, що, імовірно, на початкових стадіях коронавірусної хвороби, вірусні токсини непомітно накопичуються у клітинах кишківника, з масивним викидом їх викидом у кровотік на пізніх стадіях захворювання, що і зумовлює цитокиновий шторм і поліорганну недостатність.

ABSTRACT

With the beginning of the Covid-19 pandemic, the main symptoms of the disease were a constant cough and fever, but with the increase in the number of patients and the appearance of new strains of the virus, new symptoms appeared. More than 50% of patients experienced at least one gastrointestinal symptom. The effect of the virus on the intestine is becoming more and more obvious and requires a detailed study, since regularities were found between the presence of symptoms and a premorbid history from the gastrointestinal tract and the severity of the course of covid.

The purpose of the study is to investigate the pathomorphological features of damage to the mucous membrane of the gastrointestinal tract during COVID-19 and their influence on the development of complications, in particular, toxic - infectious shock.

Materials and methods. An analysis of the scientific literature and histological studies of the gastrointestinal mucosa tissues of 8 patients who died from complications of SARS-CoV-2 infection in hospitals of the Ternopil region were carried out.

Research results. During the morphological analysis of changes in the mucous membrane of the gastrointestinal tract, different lesions were observed over time - from signs of acute catarrhal inflammation with the beginning of a decrease in mucus formation, desquamation of the epithelium, the formation of surface erosions to the presence of areas with deep erosion of the mucous membrane. Areas of epithelialization with a tendency to atrophy were found in the jejunum. And also, thickened bare villi with stromal fibroplastic reaction, some of them formed polyp-like outgrowths with an epithelialized surface. Investigating intramural nerve ganglia, signs of neurodegenerative processes were found.

Conclusion. The described morphological picture of the jejunum is characteristic of a subacute inflammatory process with fibroplastic reaction, which is evidence of changes in the gastrointestinal tract earlier than in the lungs. As for neurodegenerative processes in the intestinal wall, they are characteristic of the wave-like course of the disease with poor clinical symptoms. Analyzing the given results, we can conclude that, probably, in the initial stages of the coronavirus disease, viral toxins accumulate imperceptibly in the cells of the intestine, with a massive release of them into the bloodstream in the later stages of the disease, which causes a cytokine storm and multiple organ failure.

Ключові слова: COVID-19, ураження слизової оболонки ШКТ, підостре запалення з фібропластичною реакцією, нейродегенеративні зміни.

Keywords: COVID-19, lesions of the gastrointestinal mucosa, subacute inflammation with fibroplastic reaction, neurodegenerative changes.

Introduction. Acute respiratory distress syndrome caused by the SARS - CoV - 2 virus, manifested by infectious pneumonia, has become the main health care problem of the 21st century. The multiorganism of the lesion is typical for the pathogenesis of COVID-19. In addition to the "classic" organs affected by the SARS-CoV-2 virus (lungs, blood vessels, etc.), sometimes the gastrointestinal tract organs can become targets. However, we would like to draw attention not so much to complications from the gastrointestinal tract, but to the process of accumulation of viral -toxic substrate in the cells of the intestinal mucosa. One of the pathogenetic aspects of COVID-19 is the binding of the spike protein to angiotensin -converting enzyme-2 (ACE2), which depends on the level of its expression in different cell types. In the gastrointestinal tract there are approximately 100 times more ACE2 receptors than in the respiratory tract, so the intestine is able to hold a

much larger viral load. Damage to the upper gastrointestinal tract is caused by the expression of ACE2 by keratinocytes of the esophagus and epithelial cells of the stomach. In addition, there is data that the virus is capable of fecal -oral transmission. The immunofluorescence study revealed that the predominant expression of the SARS-CoV-2 receptor, ACE2, occurs in the cytoplasm of the glandular epithelium of the stomach, duodenum, and rectum. Viral nucleocapsid protein is visualized in these cells. Given that gastric, duodenal, and rectal glandular epithelial cells are vulnerable to SARS-CoV-2, the above mechanism can be considered one of the reasons for its spread. According to the results of a multicenter study conducted in China, clinical symptoms such as loss of appetite (78.6%), diarrhea (34%), vomiting (3.9%), abdominal pain (1.9 %). In patients with lesions of the gastrointestinal tract, the diagnosis was delayed and also tended to have a more severe course of the disease.

The purpose of our work is to investigate the pathomorphological features of damage to the mucous membrane of the gastrointestinal tract in COVID-19 and their impact on the development of complications, in particular, toxic - infectious shock, based on the analysis of data from the scientific literature and our own observations.

Research materials and methods. Micropreparations of the mucous membrane of the gastrointestinal tract of 8 patients who died of cardiopulmonary failure in hospitals of the Ternopil region with laboratory-confirmed coronavirus infection were histologically examined. After conventional paraffin embedding, histological sections were stained with hematoxylin and eosin. The preparations were examined under an Olympus CX22 light microscope. Histological preparations necessary for demonstration were photographed. Images on a computer monitor were displayed from an Olympus CX22 microscope using a VISION Color CCD Camera and the Inter Video Win DVR.

Research results and their discussion. Microscopic examination of histological preparations of the intestines of patients who died from complications of the coronavirus disease revealed a wide range of structural changes in the mucous membrane. Different changes were observed, depending on the time of occurrence - from signs of acute catarrhal inflammation with the beginning of a decrease in mucus formation, desquamation of the epithelium, the formation of surface erosions to the presence of areas with deep erosion of the mucous membrane. Inflammatory reaction was

represented by macrophage-lymphocyte infiltration with impurities of plasma cells. Areas of epithelization of erosions with a tendency to atrophy were found in the jejunum. And also, thickened bare villi with stromal fibroplastic reaction, some of them formed polyp-like outgrowths with an epithelialized surface. These changes are characteristic of a subacute inflammatory process, which indicates the occurrence of changes in the gastrointestinal tract earlier than in the lungs.

Investigating the intramural nerve ganglia, signs of neurodegenerative processes were found, such as: ischemic changes with the presence of dark wrinkled neurons, shift of the nucleus to the periphery, chromatolysis, vacuolization of cytoplasm, swelling of cell bodies. In addition, with a longer course of the disease, karyolysis and karyocytolysis with the formation of shadow cells and neuronophagy, manifested by the accumulation of glial cells near degenerating neurons, were noted. Such a morphological picture encourages the opinion that the pathological process continued in a hybrid-like manner with few symptoms running.

Some examples of histological examination of the intestine are shown below, which revealed severe edema in all layers of the intestinal wall, dystrophic and necrotic changes in enterocytes, and destruction of villi (Pic. 1). Often, deep defects were formed - ulcers that reached their own membrane. Such structural changes were always associated with hemorrhages and inflammatory infiltration (Pic. 2).

Pic. 1 - small intestine of a patient who died from complications of Covid 19. 1 - necrosis and destruction of villi; 2 - severe edema of the submucosa. Hematoxylin and eosin staining. × 200.

Pic. 2 - small intestine of a patient who died from complications of Covid 19. 1 - ulcer formation; 2 - hemorrhage; 3 - inflammatory infiltration in the stroma of villi. Hematoxylin and eosin staining. × 400.

The analysis of literary sources also confirms that a significant part of patients who had severe complications of the coronavirus disease had minor symptoms at the beginning of the disease, their condition suddenly worsened in the later stages of the disease or during recovery.

Conclusion. Morphological changes of the gastrointestinal tract indicate a wave-like and asymptomatic course of the disease with the occurrence of a pathological process in the intestine earlier than in the lung tissue. The SARS-CoV-2 virus has a more pronounced tropism to the gastrointestinal tract, due to the large number of ACE-2 receptors, which can serve as a factor in the imperceptible accumulation of the virus-toxic substrate in the cells of the intestine, with its subsequent release into the bloodstream and causing toxic -infectious shock and multiple organ failure.

In the perspective of further research, it is planned to conduct a comprehensive morphological study of the internal organs of patients who died from the consequences of a coronavirus infection.

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